

Evaluating the Story Exchange Project: A participatory arts-based research project with Mountjoy Prison Inmates and Maynooth University in partnership with Gaisce - The President's Award

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Abstract

This article evaluates the *Story Exchange Project*, a pioneering initiative developed through a partnership between Mountjoy Prison, Maynooth University, and Gaisce – The President's Award. The project brought together young people incarcerated in Mountjoy Prison's Progression Unit and Maynooth University Access Programme students for a 13-week series of peer-to-peer workshops aimed at fostering empathy, challenging stereotypes, and promoting social inclusion. Using Narrative 4's story exchange methodology, participants engaged in dialogical and arts-based practices, culminating in a collaborative creative output—a short animation. The evaluation employed qualitative methods, including researcher participation, focus groups, and stakeholder interviews, to explore expectations, experiences, and perceived outcomes. Findings indicate that the project successfully dismantled preconceptions, enhanced confidence and self-esteem among prison participants, and broadened educational horizons for both groups. Stakeholders highlighted the project's potential for replication across other prisons and universities as a model for widening participation and supporting reintegration through education. The article situates the Story Exchange within international literature on prison–university partnerships and argues for its role in advancing empathy education and social justice in the Irish context.

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Introduction

The Story Exchange Project is the first initiative from the Mountjoy Prison and Maynooth University Partnership in partnership with Gaisce - The President's Award. Young people incarcerated in Mountjoy Prison's Progression Unit and young people in Maynooth University, were brought together in Mountjoy Prison over the course of 6 months to work towards a Gaisce award. This report describes what happened.

The Story Exchange Project was a 13-week intensive series of peer to peer empathy building workshops between inmates and university students to challenge stereotypes and create a sense of shared endeavour. It was the first concrete initiative of the partnership between the two institutions, Maynooth University and Mountjoy Prison. The project collaborated with Gaisce - The President's Award, to bring inmates and university students over 13 weeks. Using story exchange as a core methodology, the aim of the workshops accredited by Gaisce, was to support participants to develop their inter-personal skills, self-reflection and awareness capacity, confidence levels and self-esteem through examining their life experience in a different context.

Prisons and universities might not at first glance appear obvious allies, but they share common policy objectives. Universities are committed to widening access for groups who experience educational disadvantage, while for prisons, an emphasis is placed on delivering education that prepares for life after release and establishes an appetite and capacity for life-long learning. We know that education is a protective factor against re-offending, and a college qualification has been shown to have the strongest impact on reducing recidivism (Batiuk et al., 2005). The Department of

Expenditure and Reform approved an application to the Public Service Innovation Fund to break down barriers between custody and the community and to support better reintegration for people with convictions into society through education, through the establishment of a formal partnership between Mountjoy Prison and Maynooth University. Unlike in the UK, the USA and Canada, where prison and university partnerships are prevalent, this is the first cross-organisational strategic arrangement to exist in Ireland. Peer-to-peer prison exchange programmes, where traditional college students and incarcerated students are partnered together for semester long learning, have grown into an international network over the last two decades. Until now, we are not aware of any similar programmes in an Irish context. While the Story Exchange Project differs from the programmes facilitated by our international colleagues, who bring inside and outside students together to study, both create a shared learning space in a prison environment where students and inmates can come together. We believe that by evaluating our experience on the Story Exchange Project, we can contribute and further existing literature on prison exchange programmes, that all share the principal goal of building bridges and solidarity.

This report details the background to the Story Exchange Project, and how it came about, as well as the steps we took and the methodology we used to evaluate and capture participant and stakeholders' expectations and experience of the project.

Part 1 provides the background to the Story Exchange Project and how it came to pass. Information on the stakeholders involved in the project is detailed in this section; Mountjoy Prison Progression Unit, Maynooth University Access Programme, Gaisce - The President's Award, and Narrative 4; the principal methodology used in the facilitation of the programme.

Part 2 details the research methodology employed to evaluate the project; researcher participation on story exchange workshops, focus groups with participants, collaborative arts-based methodology in the form of an animation, and interviews with principal stakeholders.

Part 3 documents the findings from focus group interviews, interviews with staff, and researcher observations and insight. This section is divided in three, and focuses on; expectations, experience, and recommendations.

Part 4, the final section of the report, is a concluding chapter that summarises the evaluation report and points to 'what next'.

Evaluating the Story Exchange Project

A story exchange is of itself a form of narrative inquiry, so it stands to reason that the evaluation approach employed here drew on narrative and arts-based methods to put forward what is intended to be a vicarious snapshot montage of what it was like to be involved on this innovative programme over the course of 6 months. As well as participating on the Story Exchange Project, both university and prison participants took part in the research element, including collaborating on a creative output for the project that took the form of an animation. Graphic harvester Eimear McNally worked with us to illustrate participants' description of the project and stories from the exchanges, to give a window into the learning and bonding that occurred during these workshops behind the prison walls. Kym MacLaren (2015) describes the process that happens when university students are brought together with individuals who are incarcerated as 'magical'. Magic is difficult to describe, particularly within the constraints of academic language that is most often assigned to and expected of reports. The Story Exchange Animation, together with narrative reflection in the Prologue and Epilogue of this report, are intended to invite you to share in the magic.

Prologue

To get to the chapel in Mountjoy prison you have to first go through a corridor. This leads into a semi-circular cage-like structure with two upper floors. Through the metal grilles you can see the corridors or wings leading off to the left and right. The corridors are painted yellow, the bars white, and the metal cell doors lining either side are grey. Depending on the time of day, the doors may be open, and inmates could be congregated in the corridors and landings. The prison at these times is a noisy hub of activity.

At other times, the cell doors may all be shut, and the only sound is that of officers marching back and forth and keys rattling. You cross the circle to a narrow stair well, climb the stairs to the first floor, and then turn back on yourself to go around the barred landing in a semicircle, back in the direction from which you came. It is disorientating. The far-side steps up to the chapel have double doors made of wood, a change from all the metal, and when you enter the room with its high ceilings, split levels and huge stained-glass windows, the effect is breath taking.

There are a group of 'lads' in their late teens or early twenties seated to the right as we enter, and Niall and Marc, the two young facilitators from Gaisce aren't instantly discernible. We however, as two female, middle-aged and middle-class university staff members are. We join the circle and awkward introductions are made. There is some shuffling and nervous sniggering before Niall and Marc take hold of the situation and set us to work. I'm paired with the only young man not wearing sports-clothes. 'I've just come from the kitchen' he explains, as I pull up my chair. Our topic for conversation is 'the first time I did something', and I experience a moment of panic as I wonder what on earth I am going to share with this complete stranger.

'I'm Darren' my partner offers politely, 'what's your name again?' Darren (pseudonym) thankfully agrees to go first and tells me about the first time he played for his school in Croke Park, and it doesn't take long before I am with him. I am with him as he describes the feeling of coming onto the pitch through the tunnel, and of scoring for his team. I am with him as he speaks of his pride at being celebrated by the whole school and the school principal at the after-party, and I understand why to this day he keeps a small piece of turf from the field as a souvenir of a special day. And throughout his story, I am wondering how this boy with the long eyelashes, whose eyes are full of light at his childhood memory, has ended up in Dublin's largest prison.

When it comes to sharing our stories back to the main group, I go first. I introduce myself as Darren, 20 years old, and recount the first time I played in Croke Park for my primary school. I strive to retell the experience with all the details that matter to Darren because I am responsible for his story. It is like I have been entrusted with this very precious memory and I want to do it justice. When it is Darren's turn to speak, he introduces himself as Sarah, 45 years old. He tells the story of the first time I went skiing and nearly killed myself, making my way down a mountain Mr Bean style, using trees and barriers to slow my descent, while children, mini-pro ski champions, screeched with laughter as they sailed overhead on ski lifts. I notice how Darren's rendition of my story is a kinder version. While the story gets some laughs, he omits some of my details and retells it from a perspective that garners empathy towards my plight as opposed to ridicule.

A group enter the chapel sheepishly, and the conversations in the circle come to a halt. A huddle of terrified looking girls and guys are marshalled over to our space by the Progression Unit Governor, and I remember that they will have just walked through the cage. They are introduced as the Maynooth University students who will be joining the Mountjoy Progression Unit inmates every Friday for 13 weeks to take part in the Story Exchange Project. There is a self-conscious round of names and timid hand waves before the group is shepherded back out the doors for the rest of their prison tour. They will be starting next week.

PART ONE: The Story Exchange Project- Evaluating the Story Exchange Project

1.1 Introduction to The Story Exchange Project

The use of quotes throughout is deliberately not being accredited to any individual, which is representative of the democratic communications of story exchange as explained in later sections.

The Story Exchange Project was a collaborative initiative between; Gaisce – The President's Award, Mountjoy Prison Progression Unit and Maynooth University Access Programme (MAP). The project ran from September 2019-March 2020 and brought together young people incarcerated in Mountjoy Prison Progression Unit, and university students in the Maynooth University Access Programme for 13 workshops. All of the university students entered Maynooth through a number of 'access' schemes, e.g. the Higher Education Access Route or Disability Access Route to Education and are also part of the MAP Ambassador Programme; a volunteering initiative which promotes equity of access to the university. Part of the Story Exchange Project involved collaborating as a team on a creative output to illustrate the project, which in this instance was an animation. Participants also participated in the research element of this project, which included their participating in focus group discussions about their experience of taking part on the project.

The Story Exchange used the Gaisce Award framework, and all participants were able to use the project towards obtaining a Gaisce Award. The award was not dependent on participation in the evaluation, which was voluntary. Narrative 4's story exchange is the primary facilitation tool that was used within the programme; a global initiative that aims to harnesses the power of story exchange to

equip and embolden young adults to use their stories to build empathy and shatter stereotypes. When you're reading stuff in the media or the news or online or whatever, you always get this image of what people who are in situations like this are like. But then when you come here it's completely different. It gets rid of that stigma.

The project was the first initiative of a partnership between Maynooth University and Mountjoy Prison, supported by the Department of Public Expenditure and Reform through the Public Service Innovation Fund. The peer-to-peer aspect of the Story Exchange Project, that is the bringing together of university students and inmates to learn collaboratively has been happening on an international level in the form of programmes such as the Inside-Out Prison Exchange Program (1997), Canada's W2B (Walls to Bridges) Programme (2011), and in the UK's Learning Together (2015). There are, however, no similar programmes that we are aware of in an Irish context. Furthermore, other programmes have involved students coming together to learn on a semester long university course, while the Story Exchange Project involved collaboration to achieve an award, with a specific focus on empathy-building and breaking down barriers. Nevertheless, this report draws on the literature pertaining to W2B, Inside-Out and Learning Together and makes a contribution to the field on programmes that facilitate dialogue across profound social difference.

1.2 The Project

The Story Exchange Project brought together two seemingly disparate groups; university students and inmates, using the model of Narrative 4, in an attempt to promote understanding and break down barriers. Contemporary novelist Ian McEwan believes that story telling is not about teaching people how to live, but rather showing the possibility of what it is like to be someone else, which is the basis of all sympathy, empathy and compassion (Foster, 2007). Teaching about empathy is not the same as facilitating an empathic experience, which was the central premise of the Story Exchange as explained below.

After a series of warm-ups and icebreaker exercises, participants on the Story Exchange Project sat in a circle and shared stories, first in pairs and then to the general group. Of course, circle work, wherein participants sit in a circle and express themselves honestly while facing and listening carefully to one another, shares a kinship with Freire's (1998) culture circles and Aboriginal story circles (Baskin, 2005).

It underpins Adult and Community Education, a basis that is both democratic and humanizing, and which Freire states are essential aspects for progressive social change. The Inside-Out model used in the prison-exchange programme internationally, also starts class in a large circle (Link, 2016). As does Canada's W2B, allowing everyone to have a voice in a formation so that no one person is perceived as having more power or knowledge than another (Fayter, 2016, p.64).

Narrative 4's story exchange method, expands on the notion of story-telling and circle work, by facilitating the literal and metaphorical stepping into another's shoes by telling another's story in the first person, a method designed to foster and facilitate empathy. 'A big part of the magic is witnessing someone else relay your story back to the wider group. It requires a little vulnerability but this feeds into an alchemy of sorts' (Ruairi McKiernan, cited in McGuire, The Irish Times, March 2020).

While prisons and universities may not immediately appear obvious bedfellows, both institutions see themselves as striving to positively transform and improve society by encouraging individuals to fulfil their pro-social potential (Ludlow et al., 2019). Mountjoy Prison's Progression Unit is committed to reducing reoffending behaviour; a college qualification has been shown to have the strongest impact on reducing recidivism (Batiuk et al., 2005), while university strategic plans also commit to widening access for people who have experienced social and educational Evaluating the Story Exchange Project

disadvantage. In the case of Maynooth University this also includes prisoners and former prisoners, who are formally named as a widening participation target group.

For Gaisce, the Story Exchange Project between Maynooth University students and Mountjoy Prison Progression Unit inmates was a pilot, and the first of its kind. Gaisce has been operating in Irish prisons for over 15 years, but this was the first pairing of inside and outside Gaisce participants. There were other key differences. A Gaisce Award is usually delivered by staff in the centre, who are trained as PALs (President's Award Leader). In the Story Exchange Project, albeit facilitated by Gaisce staff trained in Narrative 4, this was a peer-to-peer-approach.

Story Exchange Workshops were delivered between September 2019 and March 2020. The programme was structured over 13 weeks, with participants working in their separate groups for the first 3 weeks, before being brought together on week 4. Below is a brief outline as to the course structure:

Workshops 1-3 - The Essentials

Mountjoy Prison Progression Unit Participants, and Maynooth Ambassadors work separately to gain an understanding of the project.

Workshops 4-6 – Building Group Dynamics

The 2 groups come together with the focus on building the group cohesion through ice breakers and team building activities.

Workshops 7-10 – Story Exchange

The group begins the Narrative 4 process and starts to engage with storytelling and story exchange.

Workshops 11-13 – Creative Output and Research

The groups reflect on their experience and explore ideas around a creative output for the project and what that might look like. They were their peers albeit on a different path.

1.3 Mountjoy Prison Progression Unit & Gaisce

Mountjoy Prison's Progression Unit was the old St Patrick's Institution (youth detention centre). St Patrick's closed in 2017, and was renamed the Progression Unit, which as the name may suggest, caters for prisoners who want and who are eligible to engage in rehabilitation services that are available to them within the prison.

The concept behind the Progression Unit is to work with prisoners in Mountjoy and other prisons deemed ready and able to start a rehabilitation process, with the intention that they might leave prison with something – a skill or a work placement, for example. The entire premise of the Unit is based on reducing recidivism (reoffending).

Gaisce - The President's Award, is a programme for young people between the ages of 15 and 25 that has been in existence since 1985. The Awards began under the patronage of then President Patrick J. Hillery, and have been supported by each succeeding President since then. Over 377,000 young people have participated in the Gaisce programme; a personal development programme that acts as a catalyst in the enhancement of positive psychological attributes of hope, happiness, self-efficacy, self-esteem, and psychological well-being in its participants (Clarke MacMahon & O'Reilly, 2015). Participants voluntarily choose to participate in the non-competitive programme, which has four

components; Community Involvement, Personal Skill, Physical Recreation, and Adventure Journey with the support of a President's Award Leader (PAL) at Bronze, Silver and Gold level.

Gaisce has been operating in Irish Prisons since 2004, beginning in St Patrick's Institution. Many young people enter custody believe they are worthless. Most prisoners have had negative experiences of mainstream education including experiences of early school leaving and expulsions (Carrigan, 2013). For many participants in custody, a Gaisce Award is the first positive recognition they have ever received (Fergal Black, Director of Care & Rehabilitation IPS, in Healy, 2018, p.1). To date close to 300 awards have been presented to individuals across the Prison Estate at Bronze, Silver and Gold levels.

To some extent they have closed doors themselves, and suddenly doors are opened 'oh you can do this' and even the smallest chink of light can often be enough to motivate them to go on and do something else. The link between self-esteem and criminality has long been explored (Morley & Fulton, 2019), and the late K. J. Lang, long-serving Director General of the prison system in Finland, said, 'all our efforts when organizing correctional services should be analysed as to their ability to support, uphold and redress the self-esteem of the prisoner' (Lang, 1993 cited in (Costelloe & Warner, 2014, p.181). The sense of engagement and personal achievement that comes from undertaking an Award programme like Gaisce, can help to restore self-esteem and act as a stimulus to engage fully in prison services (David Stanton, T.D. Minister of State for Equality,

Immigration and Integration in Healy, 2018, p. 6), and Gaisce participants' testimonies of undertaking an award while in custody, points to a transformative experience that can be both life changing and life-saving.

Lads deemed to be difficult would be participating in things, engaging, conversations would be easier. I don't think it's just Gaisce, I think it's someone taking the time out to engage with them and there seems to be a real positive return on that. The Story Exchange was able to be used by participants towards the Community Involvement aspect of their Gaisce award. Community Involvement, as the name implies, involves giving back to the community, and as most prisons engage with outside charities, in terms of Community Involvement activities there tends to be no shortage. The Buddy Dogs Programme, in which inmates train dogs for a year before going to children with disabilities is one such example. Filling envelopes with sunflower seeds to sell or making something at the bequest of a charity such as a bench or fence, or hosting a Christmas party for elders are others. One Gaisce participant in Wheatfield Prison as part of his Gold award, compiled a booklet on the charities that have benefitted from the work of Wheatfield prison, thus marking out some of the good work that prisons do and providing a much needed and alternative discourse to the one most often touted by media depicting the entire prison population as dangerous, violent, and a threat to the public (Costelloe & Warner, 2014).

Gaisce has relied very much on champions within the Irish prison system to promote its award, and Marion Irwin Gowran, project manager at Gaisce, cites Mountjoy Prison's Assistant Governor Donncha Walsh as 'possibly one of the greatest champions for Gaisce in the prison system'. In 2018, Gaisce, the Irish Prison Service in association with the Duke of Edinburgh's Award/Joint Award initiative organised a Symposium 'The Award in Custody – A Shared Perspective', hosted in the Progression Unit in Mountjoy. One of the recommendations from the symposium was that prisoners be given more ownership for their own Gaisce journey (Healy, 2018, p. 9). Following consultation with Assistant Governor Walsh and the previous year's Gaisce Award Participants in Mountjoy Prison Progression Unit, who questioned if there was parity between their experience of acquiring the Gaisce Award and the experience of those who undertake the award outside a prison setting, the initial idea for a Gaisce award that brought together Progression Unit inmates and university students was conceived.

1.4 Maynooth University Access Programme (MAP) & MAP Ambassadors

In early 2019 Gaisce approached Maynooth University Access Programme (MAP) to explore the possibility of teaming up Maynooth University students and Mountjoy Prison Progression Unit inmates, to obtain their Gaisce awards together. MAP encourages under-represented groups, such as early school leavers, mature students, students with disabilities and members of the Irish Traveller community, to enter third level, and provides these groups with support through their time at Maynooth University. In line with the National Plan for equity of access in higher education, which specifies recruiting a student body that reflects the diversity and social mix of Ireland's population, under the MU strategic plan 2018-2022, prisoners and former offenders are specifically named as a widening participation target group (p.45).

MAP runs a programme of activities aimed at removing barriers to progression to higher education and annually recruits volunteers, who act as role models and mentors to support its activities. The MAP Ambassador Programme is a volunteer programme set up by MU Student Advisor Gemma Lynch, and Access Outreach Officer Martha Brandes in 2015. MAP Ambassadors come from a range of backgrounds and have all come to the university through a variety of access admissions schemes. MAP Ambassadors are often the first in their family to have gone to college; some have come through DEIS schools (Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools); schools that are designated as serving communities identified as disadvantaged, and which show a significant gap in achievement and attainment in comparison to Non-Deis schools in Ireland (Pollak, 2019). Social background continues to be a crucial factor in the degree of academic attainment at second level in Ireland, with private schools dominating the upper end of rankings (Ó Caollaí & Mooney, 2019), and with the added value of a network that 'has a lot of weight behind it' (Reddan, 2019). The skill set acquired from being an Ambassador along with references and awards such as the MUSE award, (Maynooth University Student Experience); an award that is acknowledged on degree transcripts, adds weight to CVs and carries currency with employers. Employers stress the value of extra-curricular activities for distinguishing candidates, providing evidence of cultural fit and leadership (Stuart et al., 2011). Gaisce develops important skills such as teamwork, problem solving, coaching others, and leadership (Clarke MacMahon & O'Reilly, 2015), and is another award that carries currency with employers. As such it was seen as a way of complementing the MAP Ambassador Programme, and Gemma Lynch subsequently trained as a President's Award Leader (PAL).

1.5 Gaisce, MAP & Mountjoy

When Gaisce approached MAP with the proposal of a collaboration with Mountjoy Prison participants, MAP had just supported a research project with prisoners and former prisoners around barriers and access to higher education as part of College Connect Project (funded by the Higher Education Authority). One of the findings from the research was that this cohort experiences a high-level of stigmatization, both self and societal (Meaney, 2019). The Story Exchange Project seemed to afford an opportunity to bring the university into the prison in a very tangible but informal way, that had the potential to introduce higher education in a manner that went almost 'under the radar' and to address stigma and stigmatization for both sets of participants.

You're not going in with your pull up posters, and 'here's some information about a course'. Meetings began at Gaisce in Ratra house, risk assessments were carried out by Maynooth University and Mountjoy prison on their respective sides. MAP Ambassadors were selected by Gemma Lynch, who reached out to about 100 Level 2 ambassadors (more experienced ambassadors). A large and positive response was received, which was narrowed down and refined to criteria such as who would most benefit from this experience such as Law or Sociology students. Gender balance was also considered,

and a schedule was drawn up, the first 3 weeks of which involved MAP ambassadors being trained separately to Mountjoy Prison Progression Unit inmates. Workshops took place in the Chapel in Mountjoy Prison in Dublin on Friday afternoons, facilitated by two experienced Gaisce facilitators trained in Narrative 4.

1.6 Narrative 4

Narrative 4, a global initiative with its headquarters in New York and its first physical space in Limerick, is led by cofounders Lisa Consiglio and Colum McCann. Narrative 4 is a model for social change based on the belief that we can see the world and ourselves differently by exchanging personal narratives in a new and enlightened manner. Story exchanges work by bringing people to a distraction-free space where they are randomly partnered. They are asked to tell a story from their life, perhaps a story that might show the essence of who they are. When they are regrouped, they retell their partner's story in the first person.

The whole power of the story exchanges is when you tell their story and pretend to be the other person and that's when it clicks, it's like 'Ohhhh, this is why...'.

The programme has expanded through the US and is now working in South Africa, Mexico, Palestine and elsewhere. Narrative 4 has an impressive portfolio of collaborative projects, the aim of which is to encourage equality and empathy building, and to challenge judgemental or stereotypical opinions between incongruent groups. High School students collaborated with the NYPD and used Narrative 4 to help begin to shatter the stereotypes urban youth feel towards police, and vice versa. In Limerick, 'Boy's Stories' partnered primary school boys with men in their community to explore questions and stereotypes about masculinity, and in downtown Manhattan, members of the LGBTQ+ community, who have been bullied, sat down with members who have bullied others.

1.7 Mountjoy Prison Campus & Maynooth University Partnership

In 2019, Maynooth University Access Programme (MAP) supported a participatory action research project (PAR) to find out how to better support prisoners and former prisoners access and progress through 3rd level (Meaney, 2019). The recommendations from the research helped support targeted action response, but a significant subsidiary outcome was the building on relationships and connections that were already in existence between the two institutions; Mountjoy Prison Campus and Maynooth University. What came to light, was that while there were many individuals both inside and outside of the prison and university striving to improve the It's about inclusiveness and offering an alternative to our lads, that alternative being that there is places for you in Higher Education and in Maynooth University if you apply yourself correctly and the door won't be shut.

There is a door open for you to develop as a person, and as an alternative to crime, educational prospects for people with previous convictions, this was largely occurring in silos, so without an overall picture as to what was happening on a communal level. In 2019, Grace Edge, the MU Access Office Manager, spoke to Assistant Governor Walsh about the possibility of connecting and developing the various strands of prevailing work and charting their direction through the establishment of a reciprocal educational partnership between the two institutions. The Public Service Innovation Fund, through the Department of Expenditure and Public Reform, supported a proposal to build that partnership. Edge and Walsh worked together to bring key people from both institutions around a table in Mountjoy Prison to map out partnership objectives. The result was a charter, committing to an enduring partnership to build the diversity of the third level student population whilst supporting the reintegration of prisoners and former prisoners to society.

Though still in its infancy, prior to the Covid 19 pandemic, activities had commenced under the partnership agreement to support engagement by the university within the space of the prison and vice versa. A science and technology lecture series, facilitated by acclaimed university academics, took place in both the progression unit and in the main jail. A reciprocal large-scale and jam-packed event was hosted in the university, where Governor Eddie Mullins and a prisoner of Mountjoy currently studying at 3rd level, addressed attendees on the subject of the prison as 'home'.

The interchange of learning between the two organisations serves to deepen understanding of how each operates, and thereby create a space where it is possible to enable the development and provision of education pathways between the two. The establishment of a network on both the inside and the outside, facilitates the support of learners with convictions in a manner that reflects the learning from both sides, particularly in terms of the challenges involved in the process of reintegration. There was a lot of work happening in the university with prisoners, former prisoners and people with previous convictions, but none of it was joined up.

Both organisations, through their cooperation, have been able to take measures that might previously have been difficult to imagine. This includes the move on behalf of the Director General of the Irish Prison Service to grant inmates access to online resources and tutorials, and the establishment of the Unlocking Potential Project, to redevelop admissions policies and practises for people with serious convictions by developing a fair admissions toolkit to guide HEIs.

The Story Exchange Project, and the bringing together of inmates and university students to achieve a mutual goal, was the first peer initiative of the partnership. Facilitated and conceived by Gaisce, its inception was supported by peer-researchers from the needs analysis with prisoners and former prisoners (Meaney, 2019), who input into the project at the development stages. Its evaluation upholds the commitment of the partnership in its objective to 'evaluate and share the learning', both with other prisons and universities, and with wider society as a whole.

Award-winning artist Jimmy Leonard was approached to develop a visual identity for the Mountjoy Prison Campus and Maynooth University partnership. Leonard, who discovered his passion for painting while in prison under the tutelage and mentorship of fellow artist Brian Maguire, came through the Pathways Education Centre for Prisoners and Former Prisoners. He is currently in the final year of a Masters in fine art in NCAD and is a keen advocate for the transformative value of art and education.

The design brief was to create a visual identity that would sit alongside the Mountjoy Aul Triangle Logo and the Maynooth University logo as a visual representation of the partnership between the two organisations. Leonard created an oil painting of an abstract owl using colours inspired by the Maynooth University crest, and a quote attributed to artist Michael Cullen; 'the painter paints the future'. In Egyptian hieroglyph's the meaning for M is an owl, and there are many stories in various cultures referring to the owl as the wise one who mediates between the different animals in the forest. It is also known to be a symbol of wisdom, knowledge, learning and good judgement.

1.8 Mountjoy Prison Campus & Maynooth University Partnership - Visual Identity

Evaluating the Story Exchange Project Graphic designer and illustrator Susan Meaney drew on the vibrant colours and geometric style of Leonard's original oil painting to create options for a visual identity. The painting reminded her of a stained-glass image; a prominent feature of Mountjoy Prison in rooms such as the Chapel. The feel of stained glass together with the ancient tangram puzzles, where geometric pieces are used to create innumerable different possible shapes, was incorporated into her designs. The steering committee of the Mountjoy Prison Campus and Maynooth University

Partnership, that includes representation from the prisoner body and the prison education units, along with other relevant stakeholders were invited to select from a series of options. This is the first public presentation of the visual identity that was chosen to represent the partnership going forward.

PART TWO 2.1 The Research Methodology

The methodological approach for the evaluation of the Story Exchange was influenced by participatory arts research. As the researcher on the project, I participated on some of the Story Exchange workshops, as well as carrying out focus groups with participants and facilitating the creative output element to this project.

I do not class the methodology as participatory research however, as participants did not contribute to designing or leading workshops (Bland, 2017); but we were attentive to power relations, engaged in reflexivity, and intended participation to be empowering.

I organised focus group discussions with Mountjoy Progression Unit Participants and Maynooth Ambassadors to reflect on the experience. 17 participants began the Story Exchange Project; 9 university students, and 8 prison participants. By the end of the programme there were 13; 8 from the university and 5 from the Progression Unit, all of whom took part in focus group discussions. Of the 13, there were 5 female and 8 male participants, all in the 18 to 24-year age bracket as per the requirements of Gaisce. While the unevenness in the ratio of university to prison participants was to some extent disappointing, it was not unexpected. The Progression Unit, as the name suggests, aims to facilitate the progression of prisoners back into society, and prisoners are often transferred to minimum-security institutions to prepare for release. In the case of Gaisce, every effort is made to support completion of the award in another facility should a transfer occur.

There were two facilitated and recorded sessions with Story Exchange participants. In the first, participants took part in a semi-open discussion about their experience of the project, which had three stages; expectations around the project, experience on the project, and recommendations for how things might be done differently or improved. The second research session involved the recording of a story exchange, that participants were aware would be edited and used to present and describe the project in an animated form. The idea of the animation was first pitched to participants, who after giving consent, were facilitated to contribute a shared description of the project on an audio recording.

6 stakeholders also took part in the research; 2 from Maynooth University Access Programme, 2 from Gaisce, and 2 from the Progression Unit. Two of these conversations were paired interviews that took place remotely; the first via Microsoft Teams and the second as a conference call. The remaining two were individual interviews, one of which took place face-to-face prior to Covid 19 lockdown, and the other which took place online. Every effort was made in the development of the research element of the Story Exchange Project to ensure that the process was as positive and rewarding an experience as possible for participants and acted as a compliment to the project through the use of dialogical, democratic and participative methodology. As such, the research focussed on capturing three linked elements; participation on the Story Exchange, the creation of a creative output, and focus group and individual interviews.

There were two focus groups scheduled to take place with participants in their individual groups after the project had wrapped up. It was intended that this would offer a space where individuals could reflect and de-brief after their experience. It was also to give each group the opportunity to voice their opinions more freely. 10 days before the first of these focus groups was due to take place, Ireland entered lockdown due to the Covid 19 pandemic. While it would have been possible to facilitate an online focus group with the university participants, this would have been extremely difficult if not

impossible to organise with the prison group and could therefore have resulted in an imbalanced representation of participant voice. So, unfortunately neither of these focus groups went ahead.

On the 12th March in Mountjoy Prison's chapel there was an awards event held to celebrate the project and to present participants with their Gaisce awards. Prison participants were permitted to bring four family members to the event, and Maynooth Ambassadors were permitted to bring two. At 11AM on the 12th March, Taoiseach Leo Varadkar announced the beginning of lockdown with the closure of schools, colleges and childcare. The decision was reluctantly taken to cancel Maynooth University's participation at the event, which went ahead for the participants in Mountjoy Progression Unit, but which was summed up emotively by Assistant Governor Walsh; "We did go ahead with that afternoon. There was something missing. The lads were very disappointed. They wanted to share that day between both sets of families, between both groups. It was like the wedding without the bride."

The lockdown as a result of Covid 19 indisputably disrupted some of our plans for the Story Exchange Project, as well as preventing elements of the evaluation. Nevertheless, fieldnotes, prison participants' and university participants' story exchange, the evaluation of focus group interviews, and arts-based methodology combine to put forward a robust and thorough research evaluation and documentation of this project. Participating in workshops afforded me the opportunity to pursue co-construction of knowledge in line with the metaphor of researcher as 'traveller' rather than tourist (Hinton-Smith et al., 2018). My reflections on elements of my participation are captured intermittently and in narrative form through the report in the Prologue and Epilogue, affording a space where the reader can be invited to vicariously share in an experience, a space where imagination is a prerequisite and which traditional academic forms can fail to engender.

2.2 The Story Exchange Animation

Employing the arts in social inquiry can give those involved in the research process insight into their own lives and identities, allowing them to see themselves differently and to share their stories with an audience that is afforded a glimpse into the lives of other human beings (Foster, 2007, p.25). The creative output that emerged from the Story Exchange Project for public dissemination, is intended to foster empathy and encourage understanding. Arts-based practices can be used as a means of creating critical awareness or raising consciousness, important in social justice-oriented research that seeks to reveal power relations, often invisible to those in privileged groups (Leavy, 2009, p.13). Prisons are usually portrayed in the media or on television as either violent hellholes or holiday camps for pampered inmates. The Story Exchange animation offers a glimpse of the goings on inside a prison that many prison educators would be familiar with, but which many members of the public would not.

The creative element of the project involved two separate sessions, both of which took place in Mountjoy Prison. The first involved teasing out the benefits of using a creative device to capture the Story Exchange, followed by the audio recording of participants describing the project. This was easier said than done, and the group was split into three smaller groups and worked together on flip charts in an attempt to articulate the 'what', 'why', and 'how' of the project.

Following on from this, participants chose a line or phrase from the flipchart they had been working on that best summed up their sense of the Story Exchange and what it meant. This was audio recorded, edited, and used to form the intro to the animation. The second session on the creative output piece, involved the artist Eimear McNally joining us for a workshop. Icebreakers were used in every session to decrease the palpable tension and tentativeness in the room and give participants the opportunity to get to know each other, and the group engaged in their usual warmup activities and games prior to beginning the story exchange. This session was also audio-recorded, and Eimear, who is what is known

as a 'Graphic Harvester', drew the conversation as doodle pictures or cartoons onto large white sheets taped to the walls. The technique, which originated in the community sector as a means of catching the energy, takeaways, or inputs from workshops and meetings goes by many names; graphic recording, visual scribing, visual note-taking essentially involves illustrating the most important topics to capture the gist or essence, so fitted perfectly with the concept of the Story Exchange Project. The audio of the recorded story exchanges was then edited, and Eimear began work on storyboarding the audio for the animation. The result was a four-and-a-half-minute animation, featuring authentic participant voice, to illustrate the project and to be able to share the work in an engaging manner transferable in a wide variety of contexts.

PART THREE The Findings

The findings in this section are discussed under three main headings; Expectations around the project, Experience of participation, and Recommendations. Each heading incorporates participant feedback as well as contribution from the stakeholders. With this structure we can put forward an evaluation of the project's success in terms of participation, as well as affording the opportunity to reflect on what we would do differently given the opportunity. It is hoped that this section will be significant both in terms of capturing the efficacy of the project, and by sharing the results of a pilot project that has the potential to be replicated across other prisons and universities.

3.1 Participant Expectations

Participants on the story Exchange Project were interviewed about their expectations of participation post-project. Unfortunately, due to ethical clearance, which was secured at the last minute, it was not possible to discuss and meet up with participants prior to the project starting, which would have provided evidence of how attitudes had shifted or altered. That said, preconceptions of college students were explored with prison participants, prior to the two groups coming together as part of the preparation for the project.

Research on other projects also indicate retrospectively that many typically join initially harbouring fears and assumptions about people in the other group, despite good intentions to the contrary (MacLaren, 2015, p.373). Inmates have expressed particular concern that students from outside would think they were unintelligent and or dangerous and that they would be regarded as 'other' (Pollack, 2016, p.8).

On the Story Exchange Project, university participants spoke retrospectively about having expected there would be an atmosphere of distrust and awkwardness between the two groups. When we were working with prisoners on their own, we did a word association game and some of the lads said 'posh'.

Interestingly, this could have been a projection of what was anticipated by stakeholders, as it was clear that both groups picked up on this. Risk management strategies are to be expected in programmes such as this and address possible contingencies regarding student safety and inappropriate conduct of both groups of participants (Martinovic, Liddell & Muldoon, 2018). Nevertheless, it is worth considering the impact of strategies such as risk assessments on participant's initial perceptions of one another, and how they might serve to fuel the negative and biased mindset and thought patterns that programmes such as the Story Exchange Project are purporting to be dismantling.

"I thought we'd all be like really suspicious of each other. I thought...we'd all just be sitting in a circle, like, looking awkwardly at each other."

It is also worth noting that these thoughts and comments once expressed were met with much laughter from both groups, indicating not so much that these initial fears were unfounded, but that they had been overcome. Programmes such as Inside-Out, W2B and Learning Together, all report a breaking down of barriers and stereotypes when groups work together (Pollack, 2016; MacLaren, 2015; Ludlow, Armstrong & Bartels, 2019). A comparison could be drawn here with the Story Exchange Project, where preconceptions and their subsequent dismantling were summed up succinctly by one prison participant;

“They were nearly fearful about us coming in here and how much we shared. It’s not just poshies who go to college, and we’re not all scumbags in jail. The guy came to speak to us ... he made it seem so serious, like really scary.”

Most participants spoke of not knowing what to expect when they signed up to participate on the Story Exchange Project. Some mentioned that the initial concept seemed almost over simplistic and childish, and words such as ‘patronizing’ and ‘stupid’ arose when describing reaction to first hearing about the project. Yet listening to others’ stories and telling one’s own can be a collective sowing of the seeds of education, though it might be difficult to see this initially as we are mistakenly conditioned to see education in terms of acquiring stocks of knowledge from experts (MacLaren, 2015). Freire (1998) described this as the Banking model and advocated for embracing lived experience as legitimate sources of knowledge. The pedagogy embraced in the Story Exchange Project, which used a methodology similar to that of the other prison exchange programmes; Inside-Out, W2B and Learning Together, consider the instructor a facilitator and work to destabilise power relations between facilitator and participant and between participants themselves.

3.2 Stakeholder Expectations

For the stakeholders, the expectations of the project were more clear-cut, and could be divided into two main themes; expectations for participants, and expectations for the organisation. In terms of expectation for participants, stakeholders spoke about empathy education, and challenging stereotypes, as well as building self-esteem and opening possibilities.

It sounds patronizing. ‘Oh, we sit down, and we tell each other stories’. It sounds so stupid until you do it. It was to bring the peer-groups together and to break down barriers and stereotypes and show prisoners what students are and vice versa. With regard to expectations for the organisations, stakeholders were also clear as to the benefits they felt could be garnered from collaboration. While at first glance higher education and criminal justice organisations seem unlikely collaborators, there are significant shared objectives. Universities are committed to improving access to higher education for people who come from socially disadvantaged backgrounds, and strong emphasis is placed on providing learning opportunities within prison that are comparable with those in the community (Ludlow, Armstrong & Bartels, 2019).

A lot of what we were finding out about the higher-ed. needs of prisoners was that prisoners felt a lot of self-stigma, and the Gaisce project and the Story Exchange seemed to be a way that we could address that self-stigma. You might be from a disadvantaged area, you might not have finished school, but you’re doing the same award as the guy who might have got 500 marks in his Leaving Cert. We have been doing the Gaisce Award for the last 16 years but in a kind of a silo, behind the walls of a prison, so to make it more transparent that we’re doing the same award, the same programme as in a college.

Stakeholders also spoke enthusiastically of the sense that they were embarking on something novel in an Irish context. In addition to the shared notion that new ground was being broken, a shared belief

in the value of the project came across strongly in interview conversations across the board. For HE institutions we all have our targets to meet and we all want to widen participation and we talk a lot about intersectional disadvantage, and I think you'd be pushed to find a group with a higher level of intersectional disadvantage than prisoners.

It's been done in other parts of the world. There's no reason why it can't be done in Ireland. The time flies by when you're in here... Yeah? Wanna swap? (Everyone laughs)

The process of entering into dialogue, and becoming good interlocutors, is itself an important learning activity, a transformative experience (MacLaren, 2015, p. 380). Paolo Freire (1998) claimed that dialogue is the essence of education as the 'practice of freedom' (p. 75). Maynooth students spoke about being surprised at the positivity of the Progression Unit participants, not just in their dialogue with one another, but in their general attitudes, and how this caused them to consider the privilege of freedom and how they take this for granted.

3.3 Experience of the Story Exchange Project for Participants

Participants were unanimously positive about their experience of participation on the Story Exchange Project. Conversations during the focus groups were hugely animated with many people speaking at once. There was also plenty of joking and good-natured teasing of each other, highlighting the ease between the two groups.

The Progression Unit were amazing in bringing in an external group. It was a risk for them. The approach we were taking that we were allowing external people work alongside lads here to achieve the same award. The response and the feedback we got has been phenomenal. Both groups spoke about the bond that was created through exchanging stories, and through the dialogue with one another. This was seen to be the key in breaking down stereotypes and barriers by coming together through identification. Added to this was the model of Narrative 4, and the relaying of another's story to the group in the first person. The power of this as a model was acknowledged and recognised by participants from both groups once they experienced it in practice.

The whole power of the story exchanges is when you tell their story and pretend to be the other person and that's when it clicks, it's like 'oh this is why...'. The motivation and engagement from the part of participants inside the prison was highlighted more by the facilitators and prison management, than by the participants themselves. Their perspectives on things are a lot less bleak than how we view things, which is strange when you think about it...

In college you're always stressed. And then you come here and everyone's having a laugh. My perspectives are being changed by sitting down and having the chat, by talking to the person. You feel like you have to do it (the story) justice, and it affects you. I've never seen such ownership.

Low self-esteem and lack of confidence are continually highlighted as issues for many of the prison population, and researchers have long debated the relationship between low self-esteem and crime (Morely & Fulton, 2020, p. 101). On top of this, self-stigmatization; experienced by many incarcerated or formerly incarcerated individuals, that manifests as low self-esteem, can create additional personal barriers to reintegration into society (Evans et al., 2017). This combines to result in a sense of unworthiness that can pose further barriers in terms of deciding whether to pursue education in the first place (Meaney, 2019, p. 48). Ironically, low self-esteem and selfstigmatization can be resisted through the empowerment and motivation enhanced by education (Evans et al., 2017).

Both the prison and Gaisce facilitators remarked on the increased confidence they witnessed in prison participants as a result of the Story Exchange Project, which was exhibited in a change of attitudes

towards college and educational progression. Guys that wouldn't have been talking about furthering their education or furthering their opportunities about going to Maynooth or any higher ed. college have started a conversation.

To see college as an option for them, to see Maynooth as an option, to see any college as an option is huge. ...at that point they would never have seen themselves as ever being able to become a student.

Some of the change in attitude was attributed to an increased sense of confidence, but also was put down to the interaction with the college students and the dialogue that was occurring within the space. A change in the perception of college students was also seen as contributing to a more open attitude towards higher education institutions.

They were up there every Friday at 2.15PM waiting for the programme to start which was something unusual for us to witness.

The lads were saying, 'Oh I could never go to college', and the ambassadors were saying, 'I used to think that myself, and I'm the first in my family'.

They've seen that the students are normal people that weren't born with a silver spoon in their mouth and they've had challenges themselves.

3.4 Stakeholders' Experience of the Story Exchange Project

While the partnership between Gaisce and the Irish Prison Service has been in place since 2004, the relationship between Mountjoy Prison and Maynooth University is relatively new. The Story Exchange Project marks the first initiative of this emerging collaboration. Given the unique populations and stakeholders involved, introducing a project like the Story Exchange required careful planning and patience across all three institutions.

All stakeholders spoke positively about their experience facilitating the project, despite the considerable time and effort required to establish it. Their enthusiasm was evident in the willingness of all three partner institutions to explore the possibility of repeating the process and modelling it for use in other settings.

"It took a lot of foresight and thinking outside the box to go to this level."

"It involved quite a commitment."

There was a shared belief that the project has potential for replication:

"I think there's space for the Story Exchange to run again—it has replicability."

"I'd love to see it rolled out across prisons where possible. What has come out of it has been so positive."

"I would do it again. I've no doubt that this will become the norm here in the Progression Unit."

Stakeholders also expressed interest in future collaborations on similar projects, viewing the Story Exchange as a pilot that could pave the way for broader initiatives.

"Having this process captured and showing that this has been a really positive initiative, I hope will encourage Higher Education Institutions to want to do more work in prisons more broadly."

"We have to make time for it. There was a lot of good commitment from both sides to make sure this thing worked."

“We need to build on this success.”

3.5 Recommendations from Participants

Participants were asked what, if anything, could have been done differently to improve the project, and whether they would recommend it be run again. Feedback from both university and prison participants was overwhelmingly positive.

“If you get a chance to do it, do it!”

“It should be way more widespread.”

“I’d say if you ever want to do it again, you’d have a lot of people who will want to do it.”

Participants also praised the organisation of the project. University participants noted that the scheduling accommodated their other commitments, while prison participants confirmed that their regular activities—such as school and family visits—were unaffected by their participation on Friday afternoons.

However, some participants felt there was too much emphasis on icebreakers and introductory activities, which limited time for deeper dialogue. This issue was addressed following a mid-term programme review.

Participants also commented on the story exchange themes, noting that some were too broad and did not encourage meaningful discussion.

“Inspiration and bravery were pretty vague, and you couldn’t go too deep.”

“If you’re trying to achieve the whole ‘empathy’ thing, it’s better when you go deep.”

“Like when we got ‘a time you felt different,’ everyone spoke about emotions.”

Although the themes were carefully chosen to avoid over-sharing and to respect confidentiality, participants expressed a desire for more control over the process. They suggested that choosing their own themes would allow for more meaningful engagement.

“It makes sense what they did.”

“Choosing the theme would help because then we could control how deep it goes.”

“Like we know what our lives are like, so it’s easier to think of something.”

Facilitators faced the challenge of “holding the space” within a limited timeframe and in the unique environment of a prison. In one session, both a university and a prison participant shared experiences of bereavement. While university participants had access to debriefing after each workshop, the limitations of providing emotional support in a prison setting became apparent.

“What do you do at 5pm on a Friday? It’s very different from 5pm on a Thursday. In this instance it was fine, but it’s something I’d like considered for the next time.”

3.6 Researcher Observations and Reflections

This project employed multiple methodologies to capture its essence. These included narrative reflections in the form of a Prologue and Epilogue, a creative animation, and a report evaluating qualitative data from focus groups and interviews with both participants and stakeholders. In addition to observing the project periodically, I also participated in a Story Exchange session myself, allowing me to describe the process both experientially and from an observer's perspective.

Yvonne Jewkes (2011) highlights the importance of researchers documenting their emotional responses when conducting prison research. Over time, even the most alien environments can become familiar, and researchers may become desensitised to their own emotional experiences—despite these being deeply sociological and significant (p. 18).

Having conducted research in prisons and with former prisoners for the past six years, I find that the emotional complexity of this work has only deepened. A participant in Canada's W2B programme once remarked:

"Undoubtedly, some prisons are worse than others, but all of them can force you to address concepts such as liberty and human rights" (Carrigan, 2015, p. 67).

Researching and working with prisoners can be emotionally draining, prompting reflection on life's injustices. Yet, paradoxically, it can also be deeply rewarding and even joyful. There is a sharp, quick-witted intelligence that comes with navigating systems of poverty, policing, street culture, and abuse (Hatt, 2007, p. 145). This intelligence—often disarming and humorous—was noted by both university participants and staff:

"There's a lot of slagging—'how many students did it take to figure out where to put that chair, how many degrees?' They're so smart!"

"Bonding to the point where he tried on one of the girl's jackets, and it was up to here, 'cos you know they're so buff, they're in the gym."

A colleague with lived experience of the criminal justice system often speaks of the untapped intelligence and ingenuity required to survive incarceration. I have also observed the performative subservience of some prisoners—perhaps to demonstrate to authorities that they are deserving of educational opportunities and other privileges. This was particularly evident during the final session of the Story Exchange Project, which was audio recorded for public sharing. Several participants expressed gratitude for the educational opportunities available in prison:

"Prison is one of the best things that's ever happened to me because it's opened up so many new prospects, so many new opportunities for me."

"When I first arrived into jail, I didn't really have much aspirations... I'm actually taking part in a PT course as well, so that will be good for my CV... and I'm happy that's the outcome of it."

These comments are not necessarily disingenuous, but they do highlight the complex dynamics at play in projects like the Story Exchange. Such initiatives aim to restore self-worth within a system that often strips individuals of their identity and autonomy (Costelloe, 2014, p. 32).

Prisoners who engage in education and self-development may face backlash—both externally, through peer bullying or "slagging," and internally, through feelings of shame. A former W2B participant described herself as a "correctional puppet," a "successful and low-risk inmate." While she acknowledged that prison may have saved her life, it was through post-prison college education that

she reclaimed pride in surviving poverty, violence, and addiction—and realised that she was not the problem (Pollack & Eldridge, 2015, p. 135).

Although I remain uncertain about the extent to which free will can be exercised in prison, I have been moved by prisoners' accounts of transformation through education. Researchers have noted how often the word "freedom" appears in prisoners' descriptions of prison school, despite the system being designed to deny it (Carrigan, 2015, p. 66). I have heard prisoners describe the classroom as a "sanctuary," an "escape," and a place where "you can forget where you are."

The education unit occupies a precarious position within the prison system, relying on institutional support while functioning as a space of resistance and restoration (Carrigan, 2015, p. 66). Adult education in prison helps restore self-worth and challenges the narrative that prisoner lives do not matter (Key & May, 2019). Within this context, the classroom becomes a "back-stage" space where students can express vulnerability, resist hypermasculinity, and be seen as learners and people—not just inmates (pp. 14–15).

Projects like the Story Exchange complement prison education by enabling learning through shared experiences. Bringing together inside and outside students—who would not typically meet—creates opportunities to challenge stereotypes and build authentic connections (Fayter, 2016, p. 59). This process is central to fostering empathy, understanding, and long-term social change.

Part 4. Concluding Thoughts and Where To Next?

"It just goes to show that we're not that different at the end of the day. Our circumstances are different, but we're not different."

The Story Exchange Project brought together two groups who initially expected to find significant differences between themselves. Much of the project's power lies in the discovery—through dialogue—of all they have in common. This deepening of insight into themselves and their lived realities is a process of self-transformation. As highlighted in similar international projects, it is difficult to pinpoint exactly how this transformation occurs, but it is often attributed to the honest sharing of personal experiences. Participants themselves attest to having gained radically new insights into their own identities and the realities they inhabit (MacLaren, 2015, p. 373).

For those committed to equality, this project reinforces the need to address the issue of "othering"—the creation of an "us versus them" divide. One of the key barriers to educational progression for young working-class men is a lack of confidence that university life is for them. Differences in accent, clothing, and lifestyle can make it difficult to imagine fitting in (Johnson, 2019). Senator Lynn Ruane (2018) argues that it is the culture of Higher Education Institutions that excludes the working class:

"It's the feeling that we'll be kept out, the feeling that we'll be thrown out, the feeling that we won't belong."

In the case of prisoners, this sense of exclusion is intensified by media portrayals that demonise them through language such as "animals" and "thugs" (Lalor et al., 2007, p. 38), and by the disproportionate media focus on rare and extreme crimes (Black, 2015).

One way to counteract these attitudes is to create shared learning experiences that foster a sense of community (Link, 2016, p. 52). Initially, undergraduate students may worry about the criminality and danger posed by their incarcerated peers, while prison participants may fear elitism and

condescension from university students. However, research shows that participants typically move from an “us versus them” mindset to a strong sense of mutual appreciation and community (MacLaren, 2015, p. 372).

Projects like the Story Exchange also offer prison participants the opportunity to reflect on their lives in relation to others, which can support personal growth. When combined with storytelling—a central element in the literature on desistance (Marsh, 2011, p. 50)—this reflection can help foster a non-offending identity. For university students, such programmes provide valuable extra-curricular experiences that enhance both personal and professional development. This is particularly important for MAP Ambassadors and students from underrepresented backgrounds, who can use their experiences to connect with others and open up new possibilities through shared understanding.

“There is a huge amount of personal growth for them, and they’ll go off into various professions and they’ll take that with them. I think that’s a really important thing in terms of addressing stigma further down the road.”

By drawing comparisons with other prison-university exchange programmes—such as Inside-Out, W2B, and Learning Together—we can begin to imagine the potential for future projects that build on the success of the Story Exchange. These programmes typically bring together traditional university students and incarcerated students for semester-long learning on subjects like Criminology and Social Studies. While formats vary, they often include shared readings, dialogue, collaborative inquiry, reflective writing, and group projects (MacLaren, 2015, p. 373).

The W2B project in Canada goes even further, operating in full partnership with both inside and outside alumni, including formerly incarcerated individuals. All members of the W2B collective contribute to the programme’s design and delivery (Fayter, 2016, p. 60). Participants report a strong sense of voice, agency, and community—experiences that are both personally healing and socially transformative (Pollack, 2016).

At a partnership meeting between Mountjoy Prison and Maynooth University, Assistant Governor Walsh expressed his belief that Mountjoy could evolve into a “learning campus.” While academic interest in Irish prison officers remains limited—described as the “invisible ghosts of penality” (Liebling, 2000; Barry, 2013)—programmes like the Higher Certificate in Custodial Care (HCCC) represent innovative steps toward educating prison staff about rights and justice.

Building on this momentum, I support the vision of a “whole-prison approach” to education—one that includes both prisoners and prison officers under the umbrella of a learning campus. This model has the potential to transform not only individual lives but also the culture of the prison system itself.

Reciprocity and Future Possibilities

In response to several university participants expressing enthusiasm about the novelty of visiting a prison, one of the prison participants suggested that future projects could take place in the university—hinting at a desire for parity of experience:

“Maybe we could go to Maynooth College for a change.”

The partnership between Mountjoy Prison and Maynooth University is paving the way for this kind of reciprocity. A strong foundation of goodwill has already been established. University staff have been regularly hosted at Mountjoy for meetings, and this hospitality has been reciprocated—both prison staff and a prisoner have been invited to speak publicly at Maynooth.

In response to the COVID-19 crisis, the Director General of the Irish Prison Service amended IT policy to allow inmates access to online lectures and tutorials. As we continue to recover from the disruption of the pandemic and reassess our priorities, maintaining and developing partnerships like this requires even more creativity and commitment. However, as demonstrated by the Director General's actions, the technological advancements made during the pandemic have opened up new possibilities. These developments could allow for greater integration between prison and university spaces—bringing the university into the prison and vice versa—in ways previously unimaginable.

Epilogue

Four young women stride purposefully down North Circular Road, babies balanced expertly on their hips in matching outfits. Glamorous in a Kardashian sense, they turn heads as they make their way toward the prison.

After depositing my phone and keys at the main gate, I join another line of women and children at security. The atmosphere is subdued. There are no prams or buggies. I take the staff entrance, remove my jacket and belt, and place my belongings through the scanner.

"I'm with Maynooth University and Gaisce," I explain as I pass through the metal detector.

"More donuts for Donncha?" the guard asks, nodding at the brown paper bag in the tray.

We both know it's not for the Governor, but I smile and roll my eyes.

"They've gone through already, have they?"

"Yeah, you're the last."

I emerge onto the thoroughfare. A mother and toddler in red puffer jackets appear lost. A guard strolls over from the main jail doors, so I turn and head through the archway toward the Progression Unit. The grounds outside the education building are dotted with flowers, adding colour to the grey concrete. I swing right and enter a hallway that could belong to any public office. A guard buzzes me into the circle. We exchange pleasantries. Through the metal grille, I see a group of prisoners gathered on the landing. One nods in my direction as I head toward the Chapel.

As I open the double doors, the buzz of conversation greets me. The group is gathered in an elevated space to the left of the split-level room. For a moment, I can't tell the inmates from the university students. I'm welcomed with warm smiles and curious glances at the paper bag I'm carrying.

"What's in that? Please tell me it's a kebab?" asks a young man, prompting groans and laughter.

I pour out the contents next to a box of Krispy Kremes. Nods and smiles of appreciation ripple around the circle.

"Sorry about the kebab," I say, pulling up a chair. "Maybe next time."

"That's alright," he grins, turning back to his conversation.

The room hums with voices. Small groups and pairs chat easily, some swinging precariously on the back legs of plastic chairs. It's a stark contrast to the first meeting, when the students huddled nervously behind one another. Now, it could be any youth group in any setting.

Niall from Gaisce gathers us to our feet. We face each other in a circle.

“Elephant!” he shouts, pointing at my neighbour, who uses his arm as a trunk while we form ears on either side.

“Palm-tree!” he calls to another group, who wave their hands above their heads.

The games continue with laughter and energy, culminating in a jellybean competition.

With everyone back in their seats, mouths full of sugar, I remind the group that I’m here to plan the creative output for the Story Exchange Project. “Kebab Guy” leaves the room and returns shortly with plastic cups of water for everyone. We get to work.

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